

“But Who Takes the Liability?”: Analyzing Clinician Discourse on AI in Primary Care

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Abstract

AI systems are rapidly entering healthcare, often framed as solutions to clinician burnout and workforce shortages. Yet little empirical work examines how clinicians themselves make sense of these tools. This gap is critical as misaligned AI adoption risks exacerbating inequities, undermining professional judgment, and introducing new forms of harm. We present ongoing qualitative research analyzing public discourse among primary care clinicians to surface concerns, barriers, and sentiments surrounding AI use in clinical and administrative work. We identify emerging patterns around accountability, workflow integration, and administrative burden. This paper previews early findings and outlines a broader research agenda aimed at informing human-centered AI design and governance in primary care. By foregrounding clinician perspectives, this work seeks to bridge ethical frameworks and lived practice, contributing to safer and more equitable AI integration in healthcare.

Keywords

Artificial Intelligence, Family Medicine, Online Health Communities

1 Introduction

Artificial intelligence (AI) has become a pervasive component of contemporary socio-technical systems, with recent advances in large language models (LLMs) accelerating its deployment across high impact domains. Healthcare has emerged as a central site for this transformation, with AI tools increasingly used to support clinical decision making, automate documentation, and manage administrative workflows [31, 34]. These systems are often promoted as solutions to persistent challenges in healthcare, including clinician shortages, burnout, and rising documentation demands [7]. At the same time, their rapid deployment raises critical concerns related to privacy [22], environmental sustainability [32], professional autonomy, and the potential erosion of trust in clinical decision making [6].

The integration of AI in healthcare offers a range of benefits. Clinical decision support systems have been associated with reductions in medication errors [18], improved adherence to clinical guidelines [21], and the identification of lower cost medication alternatives [24]. In diagnostic domains, AI has achieved performance comparable to human specialists in areas such as dermatology [16], ophthalmology [33], radiology [17], and others. Collectively, these capabilities have the potential to reduce clinicians’ cognitive and administrative workload, enabling greater focus on complex decision-making and patient-centered care.

From a human–computer interaction (HCI) perspective, AI in healthcare introduces complex challenges that extend beyond model performance. Prior HCI research has demonstrated that any algorithmic system may produce unanticipated harms when introduced into real world settings [5, 19]. In healthcare, these issues are magnified by the high stakes of clinical decision making and the moral responsibility borne by clinicians. Evidence demonstrates that algorithmic systems can reproduce or amplify existing inequities when trained on biased or incomplete data, disproportionately affecting marginalized patient populations [3, 26, 29]. Accountability further complicates adoption, as responsibility for errors is often distributed across clinicians, healthcare organizations, and technology vendors [14, 30].

Although a growing body of work has proposed ethical principles and governance frameworks for responsible AI in general, HCI scholars have emphasized the gap between abstract guidance and situated practice [23, 25]. Studies consistently show that the success and safety of AI systems depend not only on technical design, but on how users understand, appropriate, and adapt these systems within institutional and governmental constraints [27, 28].

Primary care, also referred to as family medicine, represents a critical yet understudied context for investigating clinician–AI interaction. As the first point of contact within most healthcare systems, primary care providers (PCPs) maintain long term relationships with patients and manage a wide range of routine and preventative care tasks [2]. These settings are data-rich, deeply embedded in community contexts, and heavily burdened by administrative work, while simultaneously facing significant workforce shortages [7, 9]. As a result, primary care is both a promising site for AI supported workflows and a high-risk environment for unintended harms [1].

Despite this significance, much of the existing literature on AI in healthcare focuses on performance driven applications in domains such as radiology and pathology [2, 13]. Comparatively, little attention has been paid to the social and organizational realities of AI-assisted clinical work, particularly in primary care settings. Addressing this gap is essential for advancing human-centered AI in primary care and for ensuring that AI systems support—rather than undermine—equity, safety, and professional judgment in all clinical practice. While recent studies have begun examining clinician attitudes toward AI within clinical contexts [4, 15], there remains limited data into how clinicians themselves discuss and make sense of these tools in their everyday work.

Our broader research goal is to develop an empirically grounded account of how providers engage with AI systems in primary care, why this engagement differs from other domains, and how these patterns of engagement influence the safe and equitable use of such

systems. Most existing research on PCPs' perspectives rely on cross-sectional surveys or qualitative studies conducted outside active clinical settings. For example, while recent surveys demonstrate high awareness of AI among family physicians and generally positive perceptions of its utility for administrative tasks and clinical decision support [36], these studies do not include real-life clinical experiences and how AI systems are used in practice.

To develop an initial provider-centered understanding of how AI is discussed within primary care, we proposed a thematic analysis of public Reddit discourse. Reddit provides a high-velocity and relatively candid source of qualitative data for examining clinician perspectives that may be filtered in surveys or interviews. Due to the pseudonymous environment, it offers a more unguarded view of providers' everyday experiences, frustrations, and attitudes. The subreddit *r/familymedicine* is a large publicly accessible forum on Reddit specifically dedicated to family medicine and primary care, with approximately 73,000 members, 87,000 weekly visitors, and 2,000 weekly contributions. Contributors self-identify through "flairs" indicating professions such as physicians, residents, nurse practitioners, physician assistants, pharmacists, and other related roles. Although these flairs are not verified and the posts cannot be treated as a representative sample of the family medicine or primary care workforce, the subreddit nonetheless offers a rich corpus of naturally occurring discussions about clinical work, emerging tools, and professional concerns.

The study aims to characterize the range of sentiments and themes, providing a basis for subsequent, more targeted research. The content will also guide us on what specific AI tools are used and the category of AI they belong to. Specifically, we address the following research questions:

- **RQ1:** What themes and sentiments emerge when PCPs discuss the direct or indirect use of AI tools in their clinical and administrative practice?
- **RQ2:** What concerns, barriers, and risks do PCPs identify in relation to the implementation and safe use of AI systems?

2 Methods

Data were collected using Reddit's official API via PRAW [8]. We identified relevant posts using a predefined set of AI-related search terms, including general keywords and the names of commonly discussed tools (e.g. AI, artificial intelligence, scribe, DAX, TwoFold, Ambience, Vero, Freed, ChatGPT, and OpenAI). To capture discussions situated in specific clinical and ethical contexts, we further identified posts in which these terms co-occurred with relevant keywords (e.g. diagnosis, charting, consent, privacy, coding, accuracy, and HIPAA).

Posts were included if they discussed AI or AI-enabled tools in relation to family medicine practice anytime between September 2025 to January 2026. For each included post, we collected the complete comment thread to preserve conversational context, along with any user-selected flairs attached to each post. For the preliminary analysis, we capped the number of nested comments collected per post at 25 to ensure feasibility of manual qualitative coding and to support consistent analytics depth across posts, as some threads contained several hundred comments. All data collection and analysis procedures followed established ethical guidance for

research using publicly accessible online data [10]. After applying these criteria, the final dataset consisted of 46 posts and their associated comment threads, totaling 734 comments.

We analyzed the collected posts and comments using an inductive qualitative approach. We use open coding to allow themes to emerge directly from clinician discussions, rather than applying predefined categories informed by prior qualitative research in HCI [11, 12, 20, 35]. The dataset was divided among two coders, who independently conducted open coding on assigned posts and their associated comments. During this process, authors reviewed each post and comment to identify recurring concepts, patterns, and points of emphasis. The research team met to compare codes, resolve discrepancies, and refine a shared codebook. Codes were grouped into higher level themes through discussion. In addition to thematic coding, we assessed the overall sentiment of each post to capture whether discussion reflected positive, negative, or mixed attitude toward AI. Sentiments were assigned based on the dominant tone expressed across the post and its comments. This combined thematic and sentiment analysis enabled us to examine the perspectives and concerns of participants toward AI technologies.

3 Progress to Date

The discourse analysis revealed a broad spectrum of clinician sentiments toward AI tools as well as recurring themes. Mixed opinions emerged while themes of concerns, perceived risks, and barriers to the implementation and safe use of AI systems were discussed.

Positive sentiments were most commonly associated with administrative applications that offered tangible reductions in documentation burden. Clinicians reporting favorable experiences emphasized efficiency gains, improved workflow, and enhanced work life balance, often framing AI as a supportive tool rather than a substitute for clinical judgment. Providers mentioned "*noticeable time improvement*", "*giving back time for human connection*", and even a "*lifesaver*" when referring to the use of AI tools in the office.

Negative sentiments were closely tied to concerns about patient safety, accountability, and professional identity. Fear of errors with unclear liability, distrust of software vendors, and anxiety about surveillance or productivity monitoring contributed to resistance. Providers conducting behavioral health visits mentioned the software made more mistakes as it saw the patients feelings as "*fluff*", undermining the diagnosis process. Some clinicians expressed apprehension about the long-term implications of AI for primary care, including fears of job displacement or devaluation of clinical expertise relative to other more clinical medical specialties such as surgery.

Ambivalent sentiments reflected clinicians' attempts to balance perceived benefits against unresolved risks. In many cases, resistance was attributed less to the technology itself and more to imposed adoption, limited agency, and lack of workflow integration. One provider mentioned "*I was a hater at first, but I have adapted*." Overall, the current findings suggest that clinician sentiment toward AI is not binary but exists along a continuum shaped by perceived utility, trust, and autonomy.

The most prominent theme involved AI scribe and documentation tools, which were frequently discussed as a means of managing

administrative burden. Clinicians described their experiences using these tools in relation to time constraints, patient volume, and documentation quality. A provider shared that using an AI scribe now, they can finish patient notes in 3 minutes, which had been unheard of in their 20 years of practice. While some clinicians reported improved efficiency and reclaimed time for patient care, others noted limitations, including inaccuracies in complex encounters and the need for extensive post hoc editing, which in some cases reduced perceived benefits. Especially when the AI tools were not integrated into the workflow, the provider having to "create templates from scratch" was seen as reason to opt out of using the scribes in practice.

A second major theme was practical adoption barriers. Cost considerations were frequently discussed, with comparisons between free and paid tools and concerns about long-term sustainability, vendor reliability, and institutional approval. These cost discussions were often situated within broader evaluations of perceived value and return on investment. A resident noted how they use their salary to pay out of pocket for a paid scribe as the templates and improved workflow was worth it to them. Some providers noted they enjoyed the accuracy of the product but since it was not integrated into the Electronic Medical Records, they had to copy-paste the notes and did not see it as a long-term solution.

Accountability and liability further shaped the discussion themes. Clinicians expressed uncertainty about who would be responsible if AI systems produced errors, particularly in relation to malpractice risk. This ambiguity was described as a deterrent to adoption, especially in the absence of clear institutional or legal guidance. One provider said: "if this was not a liability risk, I would jump on it in a heartbeat", when discussing a new AI tool that manages prescription refills with zero human oversight. These conversations were often accompanied by ethical and institutional concerns, particularly regarding HIPAA compliance, permitted tool use, and oversight by regulatory bodies. One provider noted using AI for diagnosis is not the best idea as it will "taint your professional judgment" and create a biased diagnosis compared to an independent visit. Collectively, these themes highlight the socio-technical complexity of AI adoption in primary care.

4 Results Beyond the Short Form

Applying the methods above to a larger set of posts from the subreddit, we created a corpus and continued the inductive coding process to create an initial codebook including code definitions and a standardized vocabulary. To refine and stabilize the codebook, we applied it to additional random samples and continued coding in cycles until we reached saturation. Once the codebook was finalized, we conducted a primarily deductive thematic analysis of all relevant posts and comments in the corpus. The codebook derived from the inductive phase guided coding of the remaining data, while allowing for limited inductive refinement if genuinely new themes emerged. This analysis specifically focused on identifying recurring themes related to clinician sentiments and concerns. Themes were analyzed in context to determine the level and intensity of the expressed feelings and worries. Specifically, we produced:

- A set of recurring themes that describe how clinicians frame their interactions with AI tools in primary care, including perceived benefits, challenges, and areas of uncertainty
- A taxonomy of sentiments toward AI that distinguishes, for example, between pragmatic frustration with clerical aspects of AI enabled tools and deeper worries about patient safety, equity, surveillance, or professional displacement

These outcomes will help provide an empirically grounded starting point for understanding the landscape of AI use in primary care. The ability to map sentiments and concerns to specific domains (e.g., clerical vs. patient safety) will provide crucial insights into how perceived harms influence the safe and equitable use of AI systems, creating a foundation for future research in HCI.

The results can also guide designers on how integrating transparency into AI tools in healthcare. This includes audit logs, in app reporting tools for clinicians to flag errors or harms, and dashboards for institutions to monitor model performance and equity metrics over time. Transparency also entails clear patient facing affordances: users should be able to know when AI contributed to a clinical decision and patients should have meaningful options to consent or opt out where appropriate. These features support trust calibration and make it easier to operationalize shared responsibility across clinicians, administrators, and vendors.

AI tools in healthcare operate within a uniquely high stakes environment, particularly in primary care where clinicians make decisions that shape downstream care. As a result, these systems require clinician in-the-loop design that extends beyond token involvement. The findings of this work provide situated insight into primary care clinicians' needs, concerns, and everyday challenges, enabling HCI researchers to better understand how AI systems are experienced within the realities of frontline care. By highlighting the unique workflows, responsibilities, and constraints of primary care, these insights can inform the design of AI systems that meaningfully support clinicians while advancing transparency, accountability, and safety. More broadly, this work contributes to the development of human centered AI interventions that are grounded in the practical and relational nature of primary care and adaptable to healthcare settings more broadly.

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